

General Case Integer Subtraction

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Abstract

Vedic Mathematics is a holistic, coherent, and unified system of Mathematics. Subtraction is one of the fundamental operations of mathematics, and also one of which that pupils see as difficult. But now with the system of Vedic Mathematics, subtraction can be done with a much simpler, easier, and more creative method which can change the way pupils see Subtraction as a fundamental operation in Arithmetic and in the whole of Mathematics.

This paper shows the firepower of the sutras *All from Nine and the Last from Ten* for the General Case Arithmetic Subtraction, and with the help of the sutra *Transpose and Apply* for the General Case Integer Subtraction.

Keywords: Vedic Math, Subtraction, Vedic Subtraction, General Case Subtraction

Introduction

Subtraction, the opposite operation of Addition, is one of the operations that kids see as a very tedious mathematical routine to do next to Division. This includes borrowing and taking away numbers on the next place digit to continue with the operation.

The Vedic Method, with the use of Bar Numbers, will take you away from this unnecessary steps, and will make Subtraction easier, faster, and more creative.

With the sutra *Nikhilam Navatascaraman Dasatah (All from Nine and the Last from Ten)* and *Paravartya Yojayet (Transpose and Apply)* presented to us by Sri Bharati Krishna Tirthaji. Subtraction can be solved without doing any borrowing or taking away of numbers. First, we will recall subtraction with base numbers and positive integers which can be used only in Arithmetic, and then we will show here that the concept can be extended to negative integers, giving us a General Case Integer Subtraction which can be used in Algebra.

Subtraction: The Conventional Way

Generally, how we do subtraction with Base Numbers are the most difficult for students since it has a lot of borrowing (taking away) numbers. Other subtraction methods are done routinely and are trivial to write here.

For instance, $10,000 - 3,579$

We first write it vertically, that is

$$\begin{array}{r} 10,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Then we start with the right most number and see that the subtraction “cannot be done” since the one’s digit in the subtrahend is greater than the one’s digit in the minuend. Hence, we will borrow the value of the next digit, that is, the ten’s digit, but we see that the ten’s digit is zero, hence, we continue our borrowing until we reach the first nonzero digit. We eventually see that we will need to reach the ten thousand’s place before we can get any.

$$\begin{array}{r} 10,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Then, we borrow a value there, making the 1 become 0 since we deducted 1 from it, to add 1 to the previous place digit’s ten’s digit.

$$\begin{array}{r} 10,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

We then notice that we need to reach the ones digit, hence we continue the process of borrowing until we reach the one’s digit.

$$\begin{array}{r} 10,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Then, this is the time to do the subtraction:

$$\begin{array}{r} 10,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline 6,421 \end{array}$$

The Vedic Method, All from Nine and The Last from Ten

Using the sutra *Nikhilam Navatascaraman Dasatah*, that is, *All from Nine and the Last from Ten*, the subtraction method shown above can be done with extremely fast and easy manner. What we will do is understand that all digits are all from 9 except the last nonzero number which will be from 10.

Case I. With Base Numbers

Case I.I. With Perfect Base Numbers

Using the same example, 10,000 - 3,579.

We first see that the minuend has all zeroes except in the highest place value, in this example, the ten thousand's place. If we will have this, then we can apply the sutra. Writing them vertically, we have

$$\begin{array}{r} 10,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Using the sutra, we will think of a number that when we will add it a certain number on a specific place digit, the sum will be 9 (*All from 9*), hence giving us 6 with 3, 4 with 5, and 2 with 7. Then we have,

$$\begin{array}{r} 10,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline 6,42 \end{array}$$

Then, we can see that 9 is the last nonzero number, that is, the one's digit, so we will find a number that we will add to it, such that the sum is 10 (*the Last from 10*), which is 1. Hence, we have

$$\begin{array}{r} 10,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline 6,421 \end{array}$$

Giving us our answer without any borrowing or taking away numbers.

See [1] and [2] for more illustrations.

Case I.II. With Sub Base Numbers

Making use of a similar example, 50,000 - 3,579.

The only difference of this example from the one above is that the highest place value, which is 5 in the ten thousand's place. We will use a similar procedure as above, but we will need to deduct 1 from the highest place value, that is, $5 - 1 = 4$. Hence, we have

$$\begin{array}{r} 50,000 \\ -3,579 \\ \hline 46,421 \end{array}$$

See [1] and [2] for more illustrations.

Bar Numbers

We need to use Bar Numbers in order for us to arrive at the General Case Arithmetic Subtraction. Recall that numbers, such as 59, 38, and 87 can be represented as $6\bar{1}$, $4\bar{2}$, and $9\bar{3}$, respectively. We use this to get rid of the big digits such as 7, 8, and 9. Hence, the numbers 0, 1, 2 are shown, twice as frequently.

See [1] and [3] for more illustrations.

Case II. General Case Arithmetic Subtraction

In Arithmetic, where we all use positive integers, we have a Vedic method with the use of Bar Numbers to do subtraction in a General Case in Arithmetic.

For instance, consider $589,813 - 253,987$.

We first write them vertically

$$\begin{array}{r} 589,813 \\ -253,987 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Then we subtract: (1) When the the digit in the minuend is greater than the digit in the subtrahend, then we subtract normally. (2) When the digit in the subtrahend is greater than the the digit in the minuend, then we subtract the minuend from the subtrahend and install a bar in that specific place digit. Observe that we have

$$\begin{array}{r} 589,813 \\ -253,987 \\ \hline 336,\overline{174} \end{array}$$

What we will do then is to get rid of the Bar Numbers and convert them into normal or ordinary numbers. We will be using the sutra *All from Nine and The Last from Ten* in converting Bar Numbers back to normal numbers. Hence, we have $336,\overline{174} = 335,826$. Therefore,

$$\begin{array}{r} 589,813 \\ -253,987 \\ \hline 336,\overline{174} \\ = 335,826 \end{array}$$

One more example, $827,309 - 395,975$.

We first write vertically, and then subtract, so we have

$$\begin{array}{r} 827,309 \\ -395,975 \\ \hline 5\overline{72},\overline{674} \end{array}$$

We will convert the Bar Numbers into normal numbers using the sutra *All from Nine and The Last from Ten* twice, and we will be using the concept of Number Splitting here. We will look this number $5\overline{72},\overline{674}$ as $5\overline{7} | 2,\overline{67} | 4$, that is, we will see them as in separate parts: $5\overline{7}$, $2\overline{67}$, and 4. We will apply the sutra *All from Nine and The Last from Ten* in both the first and the second part while just copying the last part. Hence, we have

$$\begin{array}{r}
 827,309 \\
 -395,975 \\
 \hline
 5\bar{7}2,\bar{6}74 \\
 = 431,334
 \end{array}$$

See [3] for more illustrations.

Case III. General Case Integer Subtraction

We now go to the real score. From the examples in the General Case Arithmetic Subtraction, one may ask and ponder: what if the subtrahend is greater than the minuend. That will certainly give us a negative number (negative integer). Now, we extend the concept of General Case Arithmetic Subtraction to General Case Integer Subtraction using the sutras *Nikhilam Navatascaraman Dasatah*, that is, *All from Nine and the Last from Ten* and *Paravartya Yojayet*, that is, *Transpose and Apply*.

For instance, let us subtract 98,531 from 14,759.

We first write it vertically

$$\begin{array}{r}
 14,759 \\
 -98,531 \\
 \hline
 \end{array}$$

Notice that the subtrahend has a greater absolute value than the minuend. Therefore, before we apply *All from Nine and The Last from Ten*, we will first use *Transpose and Apply*. *Transpose* or flip the minuend and subtrahend, that is, make the minuend the subtrahend, and make the subtrahend the minuend. Then *apply* the sutra *All from Nine and The Last from Ten*. We then have

$$\begin{array}{r}
 98,531 \\
 -14,759 \\
 \hline
 84,\bar{2}28 \\
 = 83,772
 \end{array}$$

One catch in this method is that you must install a negative sign when you are *transposing* the numbers. Since we transposed, the final answer would be $-83,772$.

One more example, $1,958,042 - 9,899,529$

We write it vertically first

$$\begin{array}{r}
 1,958,042 \\
 -9,899,529 \\
 \hline
 \end{array}$$

We see that the subtrahend is greater than the minuend, thus we *Transpose and Apply* and likewise use Number Splitting here

$$\begin{array}{r} 9,899,529 \\ -1,958,042 \\ \hline 8,141,527 \\ = 7,941,487 \\ = -7,941,487 \end{array}$$

Another example, $2,788,137 - 6,510,819$

We write it vertically

$$\begin{array}{r} 2,788,137 \\ -6,510,819 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Then we *Transpose and Apply*. And then is to do the subtraction with Number Splitting

$$\begin{array}{r} 6,510,819 \\ -2,788,137 \\ \hline 4,278,722 \\ = 3,722,682 \\ = -3,722,682 \end{array}$$

Proofs

The Case I and Case II subtraction is already known dating from the book of Tirthaji himself. What I will prove here is the General Case Integer Subtraction with negative solutions.

Let S be the solution or the difference, A be the minuend and B the subtrahend, such that, $B > A$. Then, we have $S = A - B = -B + A$.

We multiply the whole equation by -1 , so we have
 $-S = -(-B + A) = -(-B) + (-A) = B - A$.

Hence, we can see that $-S = B - A$, that is, we can deduct the subtrahend by the minuend provided that we flip the sign of the solution or the difference.

This is where the sutra *Transpose and Apply* was used.

Summary

We have acknowledged in this paper that we can now subtract any number from any number, with any type of solutions, let it be positive or negative.

Formally, we say that the General Case Subtraction are given in two cases:

Case I. Let S be the difference, A be the minuend and B the subtrahend, such that, $A > B$. Then $S = A - B \in \mathbb{N}$ (General Case Arithmetic Subtraction)

Case II. Let S be the difference, A be the minuend and B the subtrahend, such that, $B > A$. Then $-S = B - A \in \mathbb{Z}$ (General Case Integer Subtraction)

Conclusion

We say that Vedic Mathematics is coherent and holistic, hence here we can see that Subtraction can be done now in a General Case in which pupils can now see Subtraction in a totally new perspective and seeing it not as a rigid operation to do. Hoping that this Vedic Method of Subtraction can reach our primary and middle schools so that pupils can also develop a holistic approach in Mathematics, especially in Subtraction. But as a Vedic Mathematics advocate, we will have it one step at a time.

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References

- [1] Dave, S., Fletcher, M., Glover, J., Prudente, V., Prudente, V., Ramachandran, G., “Inspirational Maths From India: A Teacher’s Handbook”, MATH-Inic Publishing, 2019.
- [2] Williams, K., “Vedic Mathematics Teacher Training Course”, Lesson 10 - All From 9 and The Last From 10, school.math-inic.com, 2020.
- [3] Williams, K., “Vedic Mathematics Teacher Training Course”, Lesson 11 - The Power of Negative Thinking, school.math-inic.com, 2020.